

Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) CoARA Action Plan

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About the Marie Curie Alumni Association

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) brings together Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) alumni at all career stages, across disciplines and sectors. Although our members share a strong background in research, their careers evolve in various directions, often beyond research. Within the MCAA, we praise this diversity and the positive impact we can spread in all areas of society. We offer our members lifelong professional development, networking, and advocacy opportunities, extending the MSCA support to benefit former fellows' entire careers. The MCAA was established and is supported by the European Commission, but is largely run by volunteer members with a bottom-up approach. MCAA has over 24,000 members from 160+ countries.

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1. The MCAA and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

Research assessment practices shape the careers, opportunities, and well-being of researchers at every stage – yet for too long, narrow definitions of excellence and over-reliance on quantitative metrics have restricted diversity and hampered the recognition of the full breadth of research contributions. The MCAA started to work on this issue with the first policy brief, 'Towards Responsible Research Career Assessment', published in 2019. The statement highlighted the growing evidence suggesting that the evaluation of researchers' careers on the basis of narrow definitions of excellence was restricting diversity in academia. Building on this commitment, MCAA signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) in 2022. As a representative voice for more than 24,000 current and former MSCA fellows across all disciplines, career stages, and sectors, the MCAA is uniquely positioned to advocate for research assessment reform that supports early-career researchers. The MCAA also operates its own internal evaluation processes (awards, microgrants, expert selections) and is working towards alignment of these with the CoARA principles.

The MCAA joined CoARA primarily as an advocate and voice for its community. Its central contribution is to raise awareness, represent researchers, and influence practices across the European Research Area (ERA) and beyond, including through active participation in the CoARA Working Groups and initiatives.

2. The MCAA's continued commitment to research assessment reform

The MCAA has been active on research assessment reform over recent years through a range of activities:

- **Policy statements and advocacy:** The MCAA has published multiple statements advocating for change in researcher culture and research assessment, available on [the MCAA website](#).
- **Active CoARA involvement:** MCAA members participate actively in the CoARA Working Groups (Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment; Early-and-mid-career researchers (EMCRs) – assessment and research culture; TIER - Towards an inclusive evaluation of research, reforming academic career assessment; and Thinking critically about university rankings network (TURN)). The MCAA also nominated affiliated member Karen Stroobants to the CoARA Steering Board, which she has been vice-chairing since December 2022, with her mandate coming to an end in December 2026. The MCAA also provides organisational support through the [CoARA Boost project](#).
- **Internal awareness-raising:** The MCAA actively raises awareness of research assessment reform among its Working Groups and national and regional Chapters, fostering community-level engagement with the CoARA principles.
- **Evidence for the European Commission:** The MCAA regularly collects feedback from its members, providing direct evidence of researchers' experiences and needs.
- **High-level advocacy:** The MCAA advocates for reformed research assessment through participation in the ERA Forum, high-level events, and public awareness-raising activities across world.
- **Participation in reform projects and initiatives:** The MCAA contributes to projects and initiatives directly focused on changing research assessment practices, including CoARA Boost, ARION, and the Peer Exchange Platform for Narrative-style CVs (PEP-CV). In addition, the MCAA is part of a [group](#)

of organisations coordinating the global research assessment reform, led by the ISC, DORA, CWTS & ASAPbio.

Building on this foundation, the present action plan formalises and deepens its commitment.

3. The MCAA's planned actions according to the commitments of the agreement on reforming research assessment

The table below outlines the MCAA's planned actions for each of the ten ARRA commitments.

Table 1. Planned actions by the MCAA for the ARRA commitments

Commitment	Planned MCAA Actions
Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather and disseminate evidence from the MCAA community on researchers' experiences of research assessment (e.g. awareness of reform, career diversity, use of metrics) through methods like surveys and community consultations. • Advocate for recognition of diverse research outputs and non-linear careers in the ERA, the MSCA, and the 10th European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10) policy processes. • Explore areas where the MCAA can recognise and incentivise members who demonstrate adherence to responsible research assessment principles (e.g. through awards, visibility opportunities, or community recognition mechanisms).
Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation, for which peer review is central, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Champion the primacy of qualitative, peer-review-centred assessment in public advocacy. • Pilot narrative CVs and application formats in the MCAA's evaluation processes.

<p>Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular, inappropriate uses of the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness among MCAA members of the harms of inappropriate use of metrics and available alternatives. • Affirm that JIF and h-index play no role in the MCAA's evaluation processes, and advocate externally against their inappropriate use in research assessment. • Develop guidance on what responsible use of indicators means in the MCAA context, in line with the CoARA principles.
<p>Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness externally and among our members of the harms of rankings in researcher assessment.
<p>Commit resources to reforming research assessment as needed to achieve the required organisational changes committed to.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designate CoARA focal points (an MCAA Board member and an MCAA Secretariat member) to coordinate the implementation of this action plan. • Continue the activities of the internal MCAA coordination group to improve alignment in CoARA.
<p>Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete a mapping of all internal MCAA evaluation processes during the first year. • Identify priority processes for reform and develop revised, CoARA-aligned criteria.
<p>Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes, as well as their use.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise webinars, workshops, and conference sessions at the MCAA Annual Conferences on research assessment reform for MCAA members and beyond. • Develop accessible communications explaining the CoARA principles to the MSCA community. • Guide internal MCAA evaluators and committee members in CoARA-aligned practices.
<p>Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively participate and represent the MCAA's researcher perspectives in the CoARA Working Groups, ERA Forum, ISC and other high-level events and initiatives. • Strengthen collaboration with partners and stakeholder organisations on assessment reform.

<p>Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish this action plan openly on the MCAA website and the CoARA Zenodo community. • Publish a revised action plan at the 5-year mark.
<p>Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribute the MCAA member survey data on research assessment experiences to the broader evidence base. • Participate in research-on-research initiatives, sharing data and findings openly in line “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. • Collect feedback from applicants and evaluators in reformed MCAA processes to enable evidence-based iteration.

4. Action plan

Phase 1: Starting phase (2025–2026)

Establishes foundations: governance, baseline mapping, and first concrete steps demonstrating the MCAA's commitment.

Table 2. Milestones of phase 1

ID	Milestone	Timing	Lead
M1	Creation of an internal MCAA coordination group towards better alignment in CoARA ¹ .	2025	MCAA Board + MCAA Secretariat
M2	Publish the action plan openly on the MCAA website and CoARA Zenodo. Designate CoARA focal points (an MCAA Board member and an MCAA Secretariat member) to start coordinating implementation.	Q2 2026	MCAA Secretariat
M3	Communicate the action plan to members via existing communication media, e.g., the MCAA Newsletter, Blog, website, and social media.	Q2–Q3 2026	MCAA Board + MCAA Secretariat
M4	Complete the mapping of all MCAA internal evaluation activities, such as awards, microgrants, elections, and expert selections. Formally commit to excluding JIF, h-index, and rankings from all processes.	Q4 2026	MCAA Secretariat

¹ The internal MCAA coordination group was created before the creation of this action plan. As it is very important internal structure, it is recorded here as a first milestone.

Phase 2: Operational phase (2027–2031)

Deepens implementation, strengthens advocacy, builds evidence, and leads to the 5-year review required by the ARRA, based on the timing of the creation of this action plan in 2026.

Table 3. Milestones of phase 2

ID	Milestone	Timing	Lead
M5	Identify internal priority processes for reform, develop revised CoARA-aligned criteria and evaluator guidance.	Q1 2027	MCAA Secretariat
M6	Implement reformed evaluation criteria across priority processes following the completion of M4 and M5. Collect feedback from applicants and evaluators.	Q3 2027	MCAA Secretariat
M7	First reflection point: building on the feedback and progress update from M6, review the overall implementation of the action plan and assess early progress on adherence to CoARA commitments. Adjust planned actions and priorities for the remaining period where needed.	2028	MCAA Secretariat
M8	Organise at least three MCAA events dedicated to research assessment reform (webinars, conference sessions, or workshops).	2026–2031	MCAA Board + MCAA Secretariat
M9	5-year reflection: self-assess adherence to all CoARA commitments, evaluate completion of the MCAA's action plan, gather member input, and publish an updated action plan.	2031	MCAA Board + MCAA Secretariat + Community

5. Governance, community and progress

Governance and resources

Dedicated CoARA focal points (including one member from the MCAA Board and another from the MCAA Secretariat) will be designated during the first year to coordinate implementation. The internal MCAA coordination group, working towards better alignment of the MCAA activities in the CoARA, will continue its activities (see M1 in table 2). Given the MCAA's volunteer-driven structure, activities are scoped to be meaningful and realistic; where relevant, the Association will seek project or partnership funding to support more resource-intensive actions.

Community involvement

Community involvement is foundational to the MCAA's identity. The revision of evaluation criteria and guidelines will draw on input from the MCAA Working Groups, MCAA Chapters, and MCAA members as a whole. The MCAA will ensure that researcher perspectives are integrated in its engagement with CoARA.

Partnerships and exchange

The MCAA has actively participated in the CoARA Working Groups and coordinated actions with peer organisations to align advocacy to represent researchers' voice at the European Commission and share best practices, including e.g. ERA Forum. The MCAA will continue engagement via these activities in the future.

Transparency and progress reporting

This action plan is a public document. A first reflection point in 2028 (see M7 in table 3) will allow for an early review of implementation and adjustment of priorities, ahead of the comprehensive 5-year review and updated action plan in 2031 (see M9 in table 3). The MCAA welcomes scrutiny and feedback from members and the broader CoARA community throughout.

The MCAA recognises that research assessment reform is an iterative journey. This action plan is a commitment to continuous improvement and honest reflection, with both successes and challenges openly shared.

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